

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

ANCIENT ALBANIAN SETTLEMENTS OF THE LIBERATED KARABAKH

Aliyeva G.I.

Doctor,

*Scientific Researcher of the Institute of Archaeology, Ethnography and Anthropology
National Academy of Sciences of Azerbaijan*

Abstract

This study article contains information about historical sites in the Karabakh region of Azerbaijan Republic, which was under occupation for nearly 30 years. Karabakh is Azerbaijan's richest territory in terms of historical relics and monuments, but these historically significant sites were left unstudied due to the occupation. With the liberation of the territories archaeological studies in the area expanded, and investigations begun in the twentieth century continued. The significance of studying Karabakh should be highlighted. The information obtained from the territory's historical monuments is critical for identifying genuine knowledge about the region. However, it should be noted that this restart in the research conducted in Karabakh should be carefully planned and done in a systematic manner.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, Karabakh, settlements, antiquity, archaeology

As a result of the Patriotic War, Azerbaijan liberated the lands that had been under enemy occupation for more than 27 years. As a result of military aggression by the Republic of Armenia 20% of the territory of Azerbaijan was occupied, more than 900 settlements were plundered, 927 libraries, 464 historical monuments and museums, 100 archaeological monuments, 6 state theaters and concert studios were destroyed. Almost 40,000 valuable items and rare exhibits were stolen from the looted museums. Currently, comprehensive work is underway to restore the infrastructure that was destroyed in Karabakh, proposals and action plans aimed at reviving various areas are being developed and approved.

One of the ancient Albanian monuments in the liberated Karabakh is the multi-layered settlement of Garakopektepe near the city of Fizuli, in the interfluvium of Guruchay and Kendelenchay rivers. In 1895, E. Resler carried out the first surveys in Garakopektepe, during the excavations of which burned square bricks were found [Abdullayeva G. 2012: 61].

In 1965, the Fizuli detachment of the Sector of Archaeology and Ethnography of the Institute of History of the Academy of Sciences of the Azerbaijan SSR under the leadership of G.S. Ismailzade began a stationary study of the Garakopektepe site, where cultural deposits from the Early Bronze Age to the Early Middle Ages were unearthed [Ismailzade G.S. 1969: 59-60]. As a result of archaeological excavations in the ancient 3 m thick cultural layer of the monument were discovered the remains of a large settlement: the foundations of quadrangular buildings made of river cobblestone, the remains of hearths, household jugs and ceramics of the 4th-3rd centuries BC. The thickness of the discovered walls was 1.5 m, and the height reached 1 m. The walls and floors had a thick layer of clay coating. F. Osmanov concluded that at that time the technique of building household and public buildings erected on stone foundations had already been improved [Osmanov F.L. 2006: 85]. The described premises, as well as other buildings of the Garakopektepe settlement, were filled

with a thick layer of ash, ashes, charcoal, burnt earth, stones and pieces of clay, indicating that there was a strong fire here, as a result of which the city was destroyed and ceased to exist [Ismailzade G. 2006: 26]. G. Ismailzade suggested that the termination of the existence of the city was associated with the eastern campaign of Alexander the Great, when one of his Greek-Macedonian garrisons was able to reach the southern borders of Caucasian Albania.

Considering the fact that as a result of archaeological excavations a medieval cultural layer about 2.7 m thick was also discovered, it can be argued that the city was renewed and continued to exist until the Mongol invasions.

Materials found at Garakopektepe testify to the significant population of this area [Ismailzade G.K., 1969]. The reason for such a long settlement of the monument in various historical epochs was the favorable strategic position of Garakopektepe. The rather favorable location of Garakopektepe turned the city into one of the main strongholds of Caucasian Albania. It was located on the southernmost border of Albania, at the intersection of the ancient routes connecting the Caucasus with many countries of the East, including the Iranian Highlands.

Another monument, also located in the occupied part of Karabakh, is the late antique settlement of Govurgala in Aghdam region. Its study began in 1958 by an archaeological expedition of the Institute of History of the Academy of Sciences of the Azerbaijan SSR [Goyushova T., 2012]. During the excavations, the remains of a Christian temple were revealed and the structure and plan of the city were clarified. As a result of the excavations, it was found that Govurgala covers a rather vast territory. Since 1969, R.B. Goyushov resumed archaeological research, as a result of which a part of the city of the ancient period was revealed and the city necropolis was explored. In 1976-77 a soil burial of the 5th century BC was discovered under the adobe wall. It proved that Govurgala is a multi-layered monument. On the basis of the ongoing excavations

and the revealed archaeological materials, as well as based on the historical literature of R.B. Goyushov concluded that Govurgala settlement is a remnant of the city of Aguen, which was the summer residence of the Albanian rulers [Goyushov R.B, 1986].

There are different opinions about the localization and naming of Govurgala. Some armenian researchers believe that allegedly in the I century BC Tigran founded the city of Tigranakert, which is localized in the area of Govurgala. After starting the excavations and a comprehensive study of the settlement and the surrounding area, R.M. Vahidov concluded that Tigranakert is localized in the area of Shahbulag, in the village of Tarnakut [Vahidov R.M., 1965]. Here, in 1751, the Karabakh Khan Panahalikhan built the Tarnakut fortress, now known as Shahbulag. After the resettlement of Armenians by the Russian Empire, they were placed in Shahbulag and began to call this area Tigranakert among themselves (in memory of the ancient city of the same name in Asia Minor -Turkey) [Huseynov R.]. Although Armenian falsifiers attribute Tigranakert to the ancient period, there is no mention of this either in ancient or in later sources.

Another significant monument on the territory of Karabakh is the three-layer settlement of Nergiztepe. The monument was located on the front line, on the border of the occupied part of the Khojavend region. In 2013, the Institute of Archeology and Ethnography of the Academy of Sciences organized an exploration and search expedition led by T. Aliyev.

Studies have shown that the monument consists of three cultural layers: Middle Bronze Age, Antiquity and Middle Ages. As a result of research in the southern part of the monument, at a depth of 2.5 m, traces of walls of a complex structure and construction remains of large oval stones were revealed. Clay and glass samples of dishes found around confirm that these building remains belong to the early medieval Albanian architecture. A large burial located nearby, signs and stamps on tombstones, inscriptions in Arabic, as well as toponyms give grounds to assert that this monument belongs to the Azerbaijani Turks.

The Republic of Armenia, grossly violating the provisions of the Hague Convention "On the Protection of Cultural Property during Military Conflicts" and the Paris Convention "On the Illicit Traffic in Cultural Property", has been looting the cultural property of Azerbaijan during the entire period of occupation. Despite the demands expressed in the UN Security Council resolutions No. 822, 853, 874 and 884 on the need to recognize the territorial integrity of the Republic of Azerbaijan and liberate the occupied territories of Azerbaijan without preconditions, the Republic of Armenia continued to pursue its aggressive policy [List of UN Security Council resolutions on the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict].

Summary

The most important upcoming tasks today are the study of the monuments of Nagorno-Karabakh and adjacent regions, the study of ancient and medieval history, bringing the results of scientific research to the attention of the world community. Research covering the monuments of Nagorno-Karabakh and adjacent regions, according to Professor Najaf Museibli, should be carried out systematically and in several stages:

1. At the first stage, the current state of the monuments known to us, as well as the degree of damage caused to them, should be established.

2. At the second stage, on the lands liberated from occupation, archaeological reconnaissance work should be carried out to discover historical monuments.

3. Certification of both previously known and newly discovered monuments should be carried out.

4. Along with all this, in a number of monuments of great historical significance and relevance in the study of individual periods of our history, long-term archaeological excavations should be carried out (11).

References

1. Abdullayeva G. Garakopektepe monument in the context of the researches of E.A.Resler and A.A.Ivanovskiy / Azərbaycan Arxeologiyası. 15 vol. No 1. – p. 61.
2. Ismailzade G.S. Garakopektepe as an ancient monument of the material culture of Azerbaijan // Izvestiya AN Azerbaycana. Baku, 1969, No 1. – pp. 59-61.
3. Osmanov F.L. History and Culture of Caucasian Albania in IV BC - III AD (on the basis of archaeological materials). Baku, 2006. – p. 85.
4. Ismailzade G. To the scientific interpretation of one of the archaeological complexes of Caucasian Albania // Problems of archaeology of periods of Antiquity and Middle Ages. Baku, 2006. – pp. 26-32.
5. Ismailzade G.K. Garakopektepe as an ancient monument of the material culture of Azerbaijan // Izvestiya AN Azerbaycana. Baku, 1969, No 1. – p. 60.
6. Goyushova T. Govurgala Albanian city ruins / Ancient and Medieval Azerbaijan cities: archaeological heritage, history and architecture. Baku, 2012. – p. 205.
7. Goyushov R.B. Azerbaijan archaeology. Baku, 1986. – p. 119.
8. Vahidov R.M. Archaeological excavations in Govurgala / Azerbaijani material culture, VI vol, Baku, 1965. – p. 180.
9. <http://www.1news.az/analitics/20110603044700457.html> / Huseynov R. «Arsak Tigranakert» —another falsification of the Armenian pseudoscience
10. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_United_Nations_Security_Council_resolutions_on_the_Nagorno-Karabakh_conflict.
11. <https://science.gov.az/ru/news/open/15465> / Jafarova N. Monuments, liberated from the occupation